

Research Article

Studies On Freshwater Molluscans Shell Diversity At Selected Sites Of Taluka Bhiwandi (Varaldevi Lake, Diwanshah Lake & Bhadwad Lake)

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ABSTRACT

Freshwater molluscans fauna are important biotic component of a freshwater ecosystems and their number and types of Species determine the health of given ecosystem. The present study on freshwater molluscans diversity was conducted from February 2024 to March 2024 at three different Lakes of Taluka Bhiwandi i.e. Varaldevi lake, Diwanshah Lake and Bhadwad Lake. Total 5 Species of Freshwater molluscs were recorded from our study sites, which belong to 4 different Order and 5 different families. Records are mainly based on Photographs and dead Molluscans shell samples, which was collected from our research area. The present Research work is mainly focused on distribution of freshwater mollusc's diversity of three different Lakes of our research area. Further detailed research work related to Distribution and the Ecology of freshwater molluscs will be carried out in future.

INTRODUCTION

Molluscans is the Second - Largest Phylum of invertebrate's animal after Arthropods found in various habitat that are divided into freshwater, marine and Terrestrial forms. Originally marine, they have since moved into freshwater and onto land, where their species number has nearly reached that of marine ones [1]. The estimate number of species of Molluscs today Varies from 80,000 Species (Boss,1971) To 1,35000 Species

(Abbott 1989), Out of these 31000 to 100000 are Marine, 14000 to 35000 Terrestrial and about 5000 are Freshwater [2,3,4]. There is Numerous Studies on the diversity of freshwater molluscs have been carried out by Various Indian researchers. According to Ramakrishna and Dey (2007) nearly 200 Species of freshwater Molluscs were recorded from India which belong to both the Classes - Gastropods and Bivalve [5]. Tripathi and Mukhopadhyay (2014) have Documented 208

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Species of Freshwater molluscs from India [6]. Recent updated research on freshwater mollusks, carried out by Mukhopadhyay et al. in (May 2017), There are 5000 Species of Freshwater molluscs worldwide, out of which 217 Species were reported from India, which includes 150 Species of Class - Gastropods and 67 Species of Class - Bivalves [7]. Western ghat is the one of the biodiversity hotspots of the world, which is rich in Freshwater molluscs fauna. According to Arvind et al (2011), Total 77 Species of Freshwater molluscs were recorded from Western ghat alone which includes 52 Gastropods and 25 Bivalves species [8]. But Molluscans fauna of Maharashtra has not been properly studied thoroughly and the Available information on the freshwater Molluscans is Scattered. Before independence few workers like Blanford (1863 1870), Preston (1915), Annandale (1919), Annandale and Prashad (1919), Hora (1925) have made contributions related to Freshwater Molluscs fauna distribution [9,10,11,12,13,14]. But after independence various researchers like Tonapi and Mulherkar (1963), Tonapi (1971), Subba Rao and Mitra (1979), Subba Rao (1989), Surya et al (2002), Patil and Talmale (2003), Magare et al (2016), Wagh et al (2019), Markad and Pillai (2020) Have made contribution [15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23]. But most of the studies were concentrated on Distributional Aspect and none of the authors studied Ecologically [24].

The main objective of the present study is to Document and analyses the Species richness of freshwater Molluscans diversity of three Different freshwater Bodies.i.e. Varaldevi Lake, Diwanshah Lake and Bhadwad Lake of Taluka Bhiwandi, District Thane. This research work is Completely focused on distribution of freshwater molluscans in our research areas. Further extensive research work related to ecological Aspect of Freshwater molluscans will be carried out in future.

MATERIAL & METHODS

Study location

Varaldevi Lake –

it lies [19.278403, 73.061612] in Kamatghar. Which is 2.6 km away from Bhiwandi railway station. It is important Largest Lake of Taluka Bhiwandi, Thane District. It is surrounded by Various kind of tree, shrubs and grass etc. It Account for 2 MLD (Million of liter per day) of water supply for the Bhiwandi Nizampur City Municipal corporation [25].

Picture .1. Shows the Varaldevi lake location and Satellite image.

Diwanshah Lake –

it is situated [19.293887, 73.046553] in Narpoli. which is 3.5 km Away from Bhiwandi railway station. It is second largest Water bodies of Taluka Bhiwandi after Varaldevi Lake [26]. Local people use this Lake for Fishing and other important thing.

Picture .2. Shows the Diwanshah Lake location and Satellite image

Bhadwad Lake –

it is Located [19.283264, 73.078253] in Temgharpada, Bhadwad. Which is 4.2 km away from Bhiwandi railway station. This Lake is generally use for religious rituals like Ganesh Visarjan and jogging etc.

Picture .3. Shows the Bhadwad lake location and Satellite image

Data Collection -

The Present study was Conducted from February 2024 to March 2024 at three different lakes of Taluka Bhiwandi, District Thane, Maharashtra. The project is mainly based on freshwater Molluscs dead shell which is found near Shoreline of Lakes. Various kinds of dead shells were collected from Three different Lakes by handpick method. The molluscans shell samples were identified on the basis of Morphological Characteristics by using handbook of freshwater molluscs of India. Records are mainly based on Photographs and dead Molluscan shell samples which was collected from Three different research areas (Lakes). Care was taken to avoid disturbance and harm to the organism during survey.

OBSERVATION & RESULT**Table No - 1 :- List of Freshwater Molluscans shells recorded from three different Lakes of Taluka Bhiwandi i.e - Varaldevi Lake, DiwSanshah Lake & Bhadwad Lake**

Sr. No	Class	Order	Families	Scientific Name	IUCN Status
1	Gastropods	Mesogastropoda	Viviparidae	Bellamya bengalensis (Lamarck, 1822)	L.C
2		Sorbeoconcha	Thiaridae	Melanoides tuberculata (Mueller, 1774)	L.C
3		Basommatophora	Planorbidae	Indoplanorbis exustus (Deshayes, 1834)	L.C
4			Lymnaeidae	Lymnaea sp (Lamarck, 1799)	L.C
5	Bivalvia	Unionoida	Unionidae	Lamellidens corrianus (Lea, 1834)	L.C

Table No - 2 :- List of Freshwater Molluscans shells distribution Among three different Lakes of Taluka Bhiwandi, i.e - Varaldevi Lake, Diwanshah Lake & Bhadwad Lake

Sr. No	Class	Scientific Name	VL	DL
1	Gastropoda	Bellamya bengalensis (Lamarck, 1822)	+	+
2		Melanoides tuberculata (Mueller, 1774)	+	+
3		Indoplanorbis exustus (Deshayes, 1834)	+	+
4		Lymnaea sp (Lamarck, 1799)	-	+
5	Bivalvia	Lamellidens corrianus (Lea, 1834)	+	-

[L.C - Least concern, VL - Varaldevi Lake, DL -; Diwanshah Lake, BL - Bhadwad Lake]

Total Five species of Freshwater molluscs were recorded from three different sampling sites of our research area, which belongs to 4 different Order and 5 different families (Table no -1). Molluscs records include 4 Species of Class - Gastropoda and 1 Species of Class - Bivalvia (Table no -1). They were *Bellamya bengalensis* (Lamarck, 1822), *Melanoides tuberculata* (Mueller, 1774), *Indoplanorbis exustus* (Deshayes, 1834), *Lymnaea sp* (Lamarck, 1799) and *Lamellidens corrianus* (Lea, 1834) was recorded during study time period. Among the recorded species of freshwater Gastropods *Bellamya bengalensis* and *Melanoides tuberculata* are found in all three Freshwater Lakes of our research area. While remaining Species of Class - Gastropoda like *Indoplanorbis exustus* were recorded from Varaldevi Lake and Diwanshah Lake. *Lymnaea sp* which is also belong to Class Gastropoda were recorded from only Diwanshah Lake. Apart from Gastropods shells, Bivalve shell were also recorded from our sampling site. *Lamellidens corrianus* which is belong to Class - Bivalvia were Only recorded from Varaldevi Lake (Table no - 2

DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

As we know Freshwater molluscs fauna are important biotic component of Freshwater ecosystems and it is also representing the health of given Aquatic Ecosystem. Patil and Talmale (2005) Reviewed land and freshwater molluscs of Maharashtra state and listed 72 Species and Varieties of freshwater molluscs[27,28]. But the Freshwater molluscs fauna of Taluka - Bhiwandi (Which came under western ghat region) are not properly studied. However some researchers like D.S Dehadray and Dr. K.B Sawant(1982) studies on Some Limnological Aspects of Varaldevi lake of Taluka - Bhiwandi, District - Thane. From this study they enlist 6 Species of Freshwater molluscs which belong to 5 different order and 5 different families [29]. But there is lack of Literature work on Freshwater molluscs of Diwanshah Lake and Bhadwad Lake of Taluka - Bhiwandi. The present Research work is only focus on distribution of freshwater mollusc's diversity in our research area. According to our Observation, Total 5 different Molluscan Species were reported from three different Lakes of Taluka Bhiwandi. Since

it's a short-term Research project, further long-term detailed research is needed to explore the diversity of freshwater molluscs and their Ecology in future.

RECOMMENDATION

The City of Bhiwandi known for its textile industries has the largest number of power loom in the country and is dubbed as the Manchester of India. These textile industries use various chemicals and dyes, but do not have proper disposal system for the waste generated during manufacturing process [30]. Apart from this the Lakes of Taluka Bhiwandi are increasingly Vulnerable due to Various Anthropogenic Activities. Pollution of Varaldevi lake is mainly due to Washing Vehicle and Clothes, Immersion of religious idol, dumping of religious floral waste and throwing of solid waste. At Diwanshah Lake regular dumping of Slaughter house waste of animals in lake, washing Vehicle etc. are source of Pollution. According to Snehal donde (2020) Bhadwad Lake is more polluted then Varaldevi lake and Diwanshah Lake as per amount of Turbidity,EC,TDS, Chlorides and Phosphorus range are far beyond permissible limit [31]. This all things put negative impact on health of aquatic ecosystems of lakes.To overcome such kind of problems Strictly monitor all of kind of Unhygienic activities like careless disposal of solid waste, bathing, Swimming etc and moving unfit industries from near lakes to other place. Proper continuous Scientific studies related to Molluscans diversity should be taken in this region. Such kind of Work will help to Assess the functional Molluscans diversity and their Ecology in our study area.

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COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

REFERENCES

1. Ramkrishna and Anirudha Dey ; Handbook on Indian freshwater molluscs :1-399. (Published by the Director, Zool.Surv. India, Kolkata); May 2007.
2. Rajendra. G. Mavinkurve, Sandhya.P. Shanbhag and N.A. Madhyasthta ; Non marine Molluscs of Western ghats: A status Review ; Zoos Print Journal 19 (12) : 1708 - 1711; 2004.
3. Boss, K.J ; Critical estimate of the number of Recent Mollusca; OCC.PaP.Moll.Harv.3:81 - 135 ; 1971
4. Abbott, R.T . Compendium of Land shells American Malacologist, Inc,. Melbourne; 1989.
5. Ramkrishna and Anirudha Dey ; Handbook on Indian freshwater molluscs:1-399. (Published by the Director, Zool.Surv. India, Kolkata); May 2007.
6. Tripathi. B and Mukhopadhyay. A ; Freshwater molluscs of india ; An insight of into their Diversity Distribution and Conservation, Aquatic Ecosystem ; Biodiversity, Ecology and Conservation. pp 163 - 195, Springer - Link; 2014.
7. Amit Mukhopadhyay, Basudev Tripathi & Abhijha Ghosh; In book : Current Status of Freshwater faunal diversity in India, (pp 501 - 525) ; Publisher : Publication division by the Director Zoological survey of India; May 2017

8. Aravind. NA, N.A. Madhyasthta, Rajendra Mavinkurve, Anirudha Dey; The Status and distribution of freshwater molluscs of the western ghats, india ; (pp. 59 - 72); January 2011 Publisher -: Cambridge UK and Gland, Switzerland: IUCN and Coimbatore, India; January 2011.
9. Blandford.WR; Description of *Cremnocochus syhadrensis* and *Lithotis rupicola* two new generic forms of Molluscs inhabiting Cliffs in the western ghats of india ; *Annals and Magazine of Natural history* (3) 12 : 184 - 187 + 4 Pls ; 1863.
10. Blandford. WR ; Contribution to Indian Malacology NO XI Description of new species of *Paludomus*, *Cremnocochus*, *Cyclostoma* and *Helicidae* from Various parts of india ; *Journal of Asiatic society of Bengal* 39 (2) : 9 - 25 + 3 Pls ; 1870.
11. Preston.HB ; Fauna of British India including Ceylon and Burma, Mollusca Freshwater Gastropods and Placypods ; London XIX - 244pp ; 1915.
12. Annandale.N ; The fauna of Certain small streams in Bombay Presidency, *Records of the Indian museum* 16 : 117- 120; 1919
13. Annandale.N and B.Prasad; Some Freshwater Mollusca form the Bombay presidency. *Records of the Indian museum* 16: 139 - 152 + 4,5 Pls ; 1919.
14. Hora S.L ; On some interesting features of Western ghats; *Journal of the Bombay natural History society.* 31: 447 - 449; 1925.
15. Tonapi. GT and L. Mulherkar ; On the Freshwater Molluscs of Poona ; *Journal of the Bombay Natural History Society* 60 (1) ; 104 - 120 + i + V + Map; 1963
16. Tonapi. GT ; Studies on the freshwater and Amphibious Molluscs of Poona with Notes on their distribution - Part II ; *Journal of the Bombay Natural History Society* ; 68 (1) : 115 - 126; 1971.
17. Subba Rao N.V and S.C Mitra ; On land and freshwater molluscs of Pune district Maharashtra ; *Records of the Zoological survey of India*, 75 : 1 - 37 ; 1979.
18. Subba Rao N.V ; Handbook of freshwater molluscs of india ; *Zoological survey of India*, Calcutta, 289 Pp; 1989.
19. Surya Rao K.V, S.C Mitra and S. Maitra ; Molluscs of ujani Wetland, P.P 1 - 115. *Wet lands Ecosystem series 2 : Fauna of Ujani Zoological Survey of India . Kolkata* ; 2002.
20. Patil, S.G and S.S Talmale ; Occurrence of a Pestiferous Land Molluscs from Maharashtra on new host plants. *Bionotes* 5 (3). 71; 2003.
21. Magare S.R, Giri.N.R and Bhavare M.K ; Diversity of freshwater Molluscs from Karanjali River, Nasik (India) ,*Int. J. Adv. Multidisp. Res.* 3 (10) 37 - 40; 2016.
22. Gajanan. A.Wagh, Qureshi . H.A and SR Patil; A brief Note on Mollusca ; Diversity from Water bodies of Amravati MS India ; *Biosci. Biotech Res. Comm.* 12 (3) : 814 - 819 ; (2019).
23. Sudershan R. Markad and Akhila.s.Pillai ; Study of diversity of freshwater molluscs from Ujani wetland Maharashtra. India ; *IFJAS* 2021 : 9 (1) : 296 - 298; 2020.
24. Aravind. NA, N.A. Madhyasthta, Rajendra Mavinkurve, Anirudha Dey (January 2011) ; The Status and distribution of freshwater molluscs of the western ghats, india ; (pp. 59 - 72); January 2011. Publisher -: Cambridge UK and Gland, Switzerland: IUCN and Coimbatore, India; January 2011
25. Techcomm Urban management Consultants pvt ltd ; Bhiwandi - Nizampur City Draft Revised Development plan of BNCMC 2023-43. Published U/S 26 (1) of Maharashtra regional and town planning Act, 1966 ; 2022.
26. Suvarna Rawal & Momin Shakir, 2017 ; [www. Bhiwandi .info.com](http://www.Bhiwandi.info.com). 2011.

27. S.Molour, K.G Smith, B.A Daniel and W.R.T Darwell (Compilers); The Status and distribution of freshwater biodiversity In the Western ghat india ; Pg No : 1 to 106; 2011.
28. S.G Patil & S.S Talmale ; A Checklist of land and Freshwater molluscs of Maharashtra; (2005) ; Prin Journal 20 (6); May 2005. DOI : 10.11609/ JoTT.ZPJ.1149. 1912 - 3 .
29. D.S Dehadray and Dr K.B Sawant : Some Limnological Aspects of Varhala lake Bhiwandi (Dist - Thane) Pg no - 168; 1982.
30. Nandita Singh and Khatib Sumaiya (2014) ; Assessment of Good water Quality in the city of Bhiwandi , Thane , India ; Universal journal of Environmental research and technology ; Volume - 4 , Issue 4 ; pg - 236 - 240; 2014.
31. Snehal.S.Donde ; Study of Physiochemical status for Augmentation of Kamvari River flow and Restoration of water quality in Bhiwandi city (MS) ; ACTA Scientific Agriculture (ISSN - 2581 - 361X). Pg No: 4 - 14; 2020.

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